

THE IMPACT OF STRESS IN PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF BURNOUT SYNDROME

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Abstract: Stress, in turn, is one of the important factors that negatively affect a person's physical and mental health, work efficiency and professional stability. Long-term and uncontrolled stress causes the formation of burnout syndrome.

Keywords: Stress, burnout, personal factor, social factor, physical health, mental health, professional stress.

Introduction.

Nowadays, in modern developments of society, the environment in which people work and professional activities are becoming increasingly complex. Technological developments, competition in the labor market, high demands on labor productivity and limited resources have a strong impact on the daily work activities of employees. As a result, all this leads to an increase in the level of psychological pressure and stress. In turn, burnout is defined by scientists as a state of mental and emotional exhaustion, apathy, and increased dissatisfaction with work as a result of constant stress related to a person's professional activities. Also, according to the classic definition of stress given by Hans Selye, stress is a response of the body to external demands and their overcoming [1]. It occurs in the form of a general adaptation syndrome of a person and consists of three stages: alertness, resistance, and exhaustion. As a result, in this third stage, the body's reserve energy is depleted and affects the mental weakening of the teacher.

This situation creates the conditions for the formation of burnout.

Also, according to the sources of professional stress and their classification. Sources of professional stress are divided into several categories: organizational, personal, and social factors. It should be noted that as a result of improper management of organizational factors, there is a deterioration in labor activity, which leads to an increase in workload, as well as time pressure and unfairness of the position. Among personal factors, the type of temperament, the level of self-confidence and stress resistance are of great importance. Social factors include relationships within the team, relationships with management and the

level of social support[2]. Also, stress in professional activities cannot but affect the performance of employees. In addition, as a result of the consequences of stress and its impact on professional activities, the negative consequences of long-term stress have been found to manifest themselves in many areas. In addition, symptoms such as headaches, increased heart rate, insomnia, fatigue, and gastrointestinal problems have been found in the body. Mentally, anxiety, depression, apathy and hopelessness are felt[3].

These conditions sharply reduce the employee's attention to work, motivation and efficiency. In addition, severe stress also has a negative effect on interpersonal relationships. Also, conflicts, misunderstandings increase in group work, and conflict situations arise with management. All this leads to a further deepening of the burnout syndrome.

Stress is one of the main factors of burnout, which leads to a deterioration in the mental and physical state of a person. A systematic approach to identifying, preventing and managing sources of stress in the professional environment is necessary. It is important to prevent burnout by creating a positive environment for employees, providing psychological support, and improving the performance evaluation system. Also, developing strategies for combating stress at the personal level helps to ensure professional stability and a healthy work environment.

References:

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